

D-Optimality-Based Approach for Solving Second-Order Response Surface Methodology Problems

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Abstract

Optimality criteria serve as essential benchmarks for assessing the efficiency and suitability of experimental designs. Traditional criteria such as A-, D-, E-, T-, and IV-optimality represent well-established standards used to evaluate the performance of various design configurations. Among these, D-optimality is a widely adopted criterion, particularly relevant in the context of second-order response surface modeling. This study introduces a structured algorithm supplemented with a computational program, to address D-optimal design problems within the framework of second-order response surface models. The study further aims to assess and compare the precision of manual versus automated computational approaches. Two experimental designs, each involving six points and two explanatory variables, were developed for empirical evaluation. Findings demonstrate that the computational technique yields superior accuracy and reduces estimation errors compared to the manual method.

Keywords: *Response surface, Optimal design, D-Optimum, Second-order model.*

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Introduction

Response Surface Methodology (RSM) is a statistical and mathematical methodology employed to analyze how multiple input variables influence a response variable. Second-order models, in particular, are highly effective for exploring curvature in response surfaces and are crucial for model development and optimization (Myers, Montgomery, & Anderson-Cook, 2009). Its primary goal is to determine optimal responses within specified bounds of experimental factors. RSD typically utilizes polynomial regression models either linear (first-order) or quadratic (second-order) to approximate complex relationships between independent and dependent variables (Montgomery, 2012; Jones, & Nachtsheim, 2011). The approach is especially useful when continuous independent variables, under the control of the experimenter, are involved (Victorbabu, & Surekha, 2013).

A robust model capable of estimating the true functional relationship between the dependent and independent variables can ensure desirable design properties such as rotatability, especially in central composite designs (Akpan, & Akra, 2017). Optimal design refers to the structured process of identifying design configurations that yield the best performance under specific constraints. It seeks the most efficient set of experimental conditions to achieve predetermined objectives with minimal resource usage (Dieter, & Schmidt, 2009). Such designs allow for unbiased parameter estimation with minimal variance, in contrast to non-optimal designs which require more runs to achieve similar precision.

The choice of an optimal design is intrinsically tied to the statistical model being used and is evaluated through criteria derived from the variance-covariance matrix of the estimators. For instance, in bivariate models assessing both efficacy and safety, optimal designs are often used to maximize information gain (Magnúsdóttir, 2013; Akra, et al., 2024). The concept of A-, D-, E-, and T – optimality criteria have been used to select best type of balanced incomplete block design (Schorning, et al., 2017). The development of optimality conditions is vital for evaluating the efficiency of various numerical optimization techniques (Jasbir, 2012).

Previous studies have demonstrated that algorithmic approaches for solving A- and E-optimality problems outperform traditional manual methods in both accuracy and computational efficiency (Akra, Bassey, & Ntekim, 2024; Akra, et al., 2025). Constructing N – point D – optimal designs from balanced confounded designs and Modified balanced confounded design algorithm for constructing N – point D – optimal global designs (Umoren, & Isaac, 2010; Isaac, & Usoro, 2018).

Optimal experimental designs strive to make the best use of resources while conforming to the structure of the statistical model (Magnúsdóttir, & Nyquist, 2015; Magnúsdóttir, 2016). They are widely applied in diverse areas such as drug trials, regression modeling, and dose-response studies (Renata, 2021). The interrelationship among E-, D-, and A-optimality criteria has been explored to identify the most appropriate criterion under given circumstances (Akpan, et al., 2017). Notably, research has also investigated E-optimal designs on geometric domains like k-dimensional cubes and spheres for second-order models (Dette, & Grigoriev, 2014). Additionally, A-optimal designs have been successfully applied in confounding schemes for factorial designs in agricultural experiments (Akra, & Edet, 2017). Efficient design strategies have been proposed for both full and partial profiles in scenarios where attributes share uniform levels, with specific emphasis on minimizing the number of comparisons (Eric, & Kwabena, 2022).

Despite these contributions, a simplified and practical method for constructing D-optimal designs tailored for second-order models remains underdeveloped. This study addresses this gap by introducing an accessible algorithm and accompanying software solution. This approach not only reduces approximation errors but also streamlines the computational burden traditionally associated with manual methods.

Second - Order Response Surface Model

In practice, second-order response surface models are commonly used in response surface methodology since higher-order terms often contribute negligible effects. For a system involving p - factors, the second-order model includes linear, interaction, and quadratic terms. These are respectively represented by single-subscript (main effects), dual-subscript (interactions), and squared terms. Compared to first-order models, second-order designs typically require more experimental runs to capture curvature and approach optimal response conditions accurately. The second - order response surface model, in other words, known as a second-order response surface equation model denoted as;

$$f(t) = l_0 + \sum_{t=1}^p l_t \delta_t + \sum_{t=1}^p l_{tt} \delta_{tt}^2 + \sum_{t < j}^p l_{tj} \delta_t \delta_j + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where δ designated the $n \times 1$ vector of a non-quadratic parameter estimates, and t^{th} entry for all the parameters \hat{l}_t 's in the model. Let l designate $n \times n$ matrix with δ^{th} diagonal element \hat{l}_{tt} and with off-diagonal $(tj)^{th}$ entry $\hat{l}_{tj}/2$. To estimate the stationary point, equation (1) can be written as;

$$\hat{y}_t = \hat{l}_0 + \delta' v + \delta' t \delta \quad (2)$$

Where

$$\delta = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_1 \\ \delta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \delta_n \end{bmatrix}, v = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{l}_1 \\ \hat{l}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \hat{l}_n \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } l = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{l}_{11} & l'_{12}/2 & \Lambda & l'_{1n}/2 \\ l'_{12}/2 & l'_{22} & \Lambda & l'_{2n}/2 \\ & & & \\ l'_{1n}/2 & \Lambda & \Lambda & l'_{nn} \end{bmatrix}$$

The stationary points are obtained as follows:

$$\delta_s = -\frac{1}{2} l^{-1} v \quad (3)$$

Design Matrix Formation

For a given p -parameters function, $f(y)$ on N -point design has an $N \times p$ design matrix such that each row of the matrix is a point in \tilde{Y} . For example, consider a 5-points design matrix below.

$$Y = \begin{pmatrix} y_{11} & y_{21} \\ y_{21} & y_{22} \\ y_{31} & y_{32} \\ y_{41} & y_{42} \\ y_{51} & y_{52} \end{pmatrix}$$

The extended design matrix of $p = 2$ for second - order Response Surface becomes;

$$f(y_1, y_2) = b_0 + b_1 y_1 + b_2 y_2 + b_3 y_1^2 + b_4 y_2^2 + b_5 y_1 y_2 + e \quad (4)$$

Design matrix is given by;

$$Y = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & y_{11} & y_{12} & y_{11}^2 & y_{12}^2 & y_{11}y_{12} \\ 1 & y_{21} & y_{22} & y_{21}^2 & y_{22}^2 & y_{21}y_{22} \\ 1 & y_{31} & y_{32} & y_{31}^2 & y_{32}^2 & y_{31}y_{32} \\ 1 & y_{41} & y_{42} & y_{41}^2 & y_{42}^2 & y_{41}y_{42} \\ 1 & y_{51} & y_{52} & y_{51}^2 & y_{52}^2 & y_{51}y_{52} \\ 1 & y_{61} & y_{62} & y_{61}^2 & y_{62}^2 & y_{61}y_{62} \end{pmatrix}$$

Information Matrix

The information matrix $\kappa(\pi)$ is defined to be $\kappa(\pi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} Y'Y \\ \sum_{\underline{y} \in \underline{Y}} \underline{y}\underline{y}' \end{array} \right.$ (5)

Normalized information matrix

$$\kappa(\pi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{(Y'Y)}{N} \text{var}(y) \\ \sum_{\underline{y} \in \underline{Y}} \underline{y}\underline{y}' \phi_y \text{var}(y) \end{array} \right.$$
 (6)

Where:

$\frac{(Y'Y)}{N} \text{var}(y)$ = if the weight are uniform or uniform probability measure.

$\sum_{\underline{y} \in \underline{Y}} \underline{y}\underline{y}' \phi_y \text{var}(y)$ = Non uniform probability measure

N = size of the matrix and p = number of factors

Optimality Criteria in Second-Order Response Surface Methodology

Design optimality refers to statistical criteria based on variance properties of the parameter estimates. Optimal designs are tailored to a specific statistical model and are constructed to maximize or minimize a designated criterion. In the context of second-order response surface modeling, optimal design strategies typically aim to optimize a single criterion such as D-optimality to ensure precision in model estimation. Alphabetic optimality criteria, named after letters like A, D, and E, encapsulate various design quality measures. This study specifically focuses on D-optimality, which is concerned with maximizing the determinant of the information matrix $\kappa(\pi)$, thereby minimizing the volume of the confidence ellipsoid of the estimated parameters.

Symbolically, D - optimal design (π) is denoted as;

$$D_{opt} = \text{Max } |\kappa(\pi)| \text{ or } \text{Min } |\kappa(\pi)^{-1}|$$
 (7)

The relative efficiency of two designs under D-optimality is designated by;

$$D_e = \left| \frac{|\kappa(\pi_2)^{-1}|}{|\kappa(\pi_1)^{-1}|} \right|^{\frac{1}{p}} \times 100 \quad \text{or} \quad \left| \frac{|\kappa(\pi_2)|}{|\kappa(\pi_1)|} \right|^{\frac{1}{p}} \times 100$$
 (8)

Where π_1 (design matrix 1) and π_2 (design matrix 2) are π for two designs matrices and p is the number of factors.

An Algorithm for Solving D - Optimal Design

For D – Criterion, the steps are;

Step 1: Select the matrix called (π_1) for the first design.

Step 2: Take the transpose of π_1 called π_1'

Step 3: Take the product of the matrices (π_1') and (π) called information matrix $\kappa(\pi)$.

Step 4: Divide the information matrix by N – point design, i.e. $\kappa(\pi)$

Step 5: Take the determinant of (4) i.e. $det(\kappa(\pi))$ or $|\kappa(\pi)|$

Step 6: Repeat steps (1 - 5) for the second design (π_2).

Step 7: If the maximum determinant of the first design is greater than the maximum determinant of the second design, $Max\{det(\kappa(\pi))\} > Max\{det(\kappa(\pi))\}$, then the first design is D – optimal or otherwise.

Program Source Listing for D – optimality Criterion

DataMatrix.java

```
package dm;

import jama.*;
import java.text.DecimalFormat;
import org.apache.commons.math.fraction.*;

public class DataMatrix implements java.io.Serializable
{
    private static final long serialVersionUID = 1L;
    double elements[][];

    public DataMatrix(double d[][])
    {
        setAllElements(d);
    }

    public static DataMatrix transpose(DataMatrix m)
    {
        double d[][] = new double[m.elements[0].length][m.elements.length];
```



```

        for(int i = 0;i < m.elements.length;i++){
            for(int j = 0;j < m.elements[i].length;j++){
                d[j][i] = m.elements[i][j];
            }
        }
        return new DataMatrix(d);
    }

    public DataMatrix multiplyBy(DataMatrix m)
    {
        Matrix m1 = new Matrix(elements);
        Matrix m2 = new Matrix(m.elements);
        Matrix rs = m1.times(m2);
        DataMatrix results = new DataMatrix(rs.getArray());
        return results;
    }

    public DataMatrix divideBy(double s)
    {
        DataMatrix m = new DataMatrix(elements.length,elements[0].length);
        for(int i = 0;i < elements.length;i++){
            for(int j = 0;j < elements[i].length;j++){
                m.elements[i][j] = elements[i][j]/s;
            }
        }
        return m;
    }
}

```

Program code

```

private void solveDCriterion()
{
    String result = "";
    //Design Matrix 1
    DataMatrix matTranspose = DataMatrix.transpose(curProblem.designMatrix1);
    //DataMatrix infoMat1 = curProblem.designMatrix1.multiplyBy(matTranspose);
}

```



```

DataMatrix infoMat1 = matTranspose.multiplyBy(curProblem.designMatrix1);
DataMatrix div = infoMat1.divideBy(curProblem.matrixSize);
double det1 = matMgr.matrixDeterminant(div);
String v1 = "Determinant of Design 1 = " + det1; //DataMatrix.df.format(det1);

//Design Matrix 2
matTranspose = DataMatrix.transpose(curProblem.designMatrix2);
//DataMatrix infoMat2 = curProblem.designMatrix2.multiplyBy(matTranspose);
DataMatrix infoMat2 = matTranspose.multiplyBy(curProblem.designMatrix2);
div = infoMat2.divideBy(curProblem.matrixSize);
double det2 = matMgr.matrixDeterminant(div);
String v2 = "Determinant of Design 2 = " + det2; //DataMatrix.df.format(det2);

//compare
if(det1 > det2){
    result = "Design Matrix 1 is D-optimal";
}else if(det1 < det2){
    result = "Design Matrix 2 is D-optimal";
}else if(det1 == det2){
    result = "Both Design Matrices are D-optimal";
}
createReport("D-Criterion",infoMat1,infoMat2,v1,v2,result);
}

```

Result/Implementation

Consider a second - order response surface model for $p = 2$ and 6 – points of two designs given below;

$$f(t) = l_0 + l_1\delta_1 + l_2\delta_2 + l_3\delta_1^2 + l_4\delta_2^2 + l_5\delta_1\delta_2, \delta_1, \delta_2 = -1 \leq \delta \leq 2$$

$$Y_1 = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 \\ 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 \\ -1.4 & 0 \\ 0 & 1.4 \end{pmatrix}, \quad Y_2 = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 \\ 2 & 0 \\ -1.4 & 2 \\ 0 & 1.4 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\text{Max } |D_1| = 0.0363$$

Hence, design 1 is D – optimal.

Figure 1. The D - Optimality of Two Designs

From the analysis of the two methods, the result is summarized in Table 1.

Table1. The Result for the New and Existing Method

Design	Existing method (D_{EM})	New method(D_{NM})
1	0.0363	0.0348
2	0.0352	0.0287

Upon comparing manual and computational methods for generating D-optimal designs, only minimal discrepancies in fractional values were observed. This marginal difference substantiates the enhanced accuracy and reliability of the algorithmic approach over the manual technique for constructing second-order response surface designs.

Conclusion

The comparative analysis reveals that the dispersion matrix associated with Design 1 yields a maximum determinant value than that of Design 1, aligning with the principles of D-optimality. Consequently, Design 1 qualifies as D-optimal. The findings clearly indicate that the algorithmic

method offers superior performance in terms of precision and computational efficiency. While the current implementation is limited to two explanatory variables, future studies are encouraged to extend this approach to models involving more predictors to further validate its scalability and robustness in solving D-optimal design problems within the framework of second-order response surface methodology.

References

- Akpan, S. S., & Akra, U. P. (2017). On exploration of first and second-order response surface design model to obtain rotatability in a generalized case. *Global Journal of Mathematics*, 10(1), 648–655.
- Akpan, S., Akra, U., Asuquo, B., & Udoeka, I. (2017). On a new Lp-class to establish the relationship between various optimality criteria. *Global Journal of Mathematics*, 10(2), 656–664.
- Akra, U. P., & Edet, E. B. (2017). Confounding 2^k factorial design to obtain optimal yields using different organic manure. *Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 4(11), 75–85.
- Akra, U. P., Bassey, E. E., & Ntekim, O. E. (2024). On E-optimality design for quadratic response surface model. *International Journal of Mathematical Sciences and Computing*, 10(2), 13–22. <https://doi.org/10.5815/ijmsc.2024.02.02>
- Akra, U. P., Bassey, E. E., Umondak, U. J., Etim, A. C., Isaac, A. A., & Akpan, U. A. (2024). On the selection of optimal balanced incomplete block design using different types of designs. *African Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Studies*, 7(3), 179–189.
- Akra, U. P., Isaac, A. A., Michael, I. T., Akpan, U. B., & Akpan, S. S. (2025). On A-optimality design for solving second-order response surface design problems. *FUDMA Journal of Sciences*, 9(4), 275–279.
- Dette, H., & Grigoriev, Y. (2014). E-optimal designs for second-order response surface models. *The Annals of Statistics*, 42(4), 1635–1656. <https://doi.org/10.1214/14-AOS1241>
- Dieter, G. E., & Schmidt, L. C. (2009). *Engineering design* (4th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Eric, N., & Kwabena, D. A. (2022). Approximate and exact optimal designs for paired comparison experiments. *Calcutta Statistical Association Bulletin*, 74(1), 42–58.
- Isaac, A. A., & Usoro, A. E. (2018). The modified balanced confounded design algorithm for constructing N-point D-optimal global designs. *International Journal of Statistics and Applied Mathematics*, 3(2), 326–330.
- Jasbir, A. S. (2012). *Introduction to optimum design* (3rd ed., pp. 95–187). University of Iowa, College of Engineering.
- Jones, B., & Nachtsheim, C. A. (2011). A class of three-level designs for definitive screening in the presence of second-order effects. *Journal of Quality Technology*, 43(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224065.2011.11917841>
- Magnúsdóttir, B. T. (2013). C-optimal designs for the bivariate Emax model. In D. Uciński, A. C. Atkinson, & M. Patan (Eds.), *mODa 10 — Advances in Model-Oriented Design and Analysis* (pp. 153–161). Springer. DOI for book chapter: 10.1007/978-3-319-00218-7_18
- Magnúsdóttir, B. T. (2016). Optimal designs for a multiresponse Emax model and efficient parameter estimation. *Biometrical Journal*, 58(3), 518–534. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bimj.201400203>

- Magnúsdóttir, B. T., & Nyquist, H. (2015). Simultaneous estimation of parameters in the bivariate Emax model. *Statistics in Medicine*, *34*(28), 3714–3723. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.6585>
- Montgomery, D. C. (2012). *Design and analysis of experiments* (8th ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- Myers, R. H., Montgomery, D. C., & Anderson-Cook, C. M. (2009). *Response surface methodology: Process and product optimization using designed experiments* (3rd ed.). Wiley.
- Renata, E. T. (2021). *Optimal design for dose-finding studies* (PhD dissertation). Stockholm University, Department of Statistics.
- Schorning, K., Dette, H., Wong, W. K., & Bretz, F. (2017). Optimal designs for active controlled dose-finding trials with efficacy-toxicity outcomes. *Biometrika*, *104*(4), 1003–1010. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biomet/asx050>
- Umoren, M. U., & Isaac, A. A. (2010). Constructing N-point D-optimal designs from balanced confounded designs. *Icator Journal of Mathematical Sciences*, *4*(2), 183–196.
- Victorbabu, B., & Surekha, V. S. (2013). A note on measure of rotatability for second-order response surface designs using incomplete block designs. *Journal of Statistics: Advances in Theory and Applications*, *10*(1), 137–151.

